

APPLICATION OF LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (LMS) IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (HEIs)

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ABSTRACT

Learning Management System (LMS) is a web based or cloud-based software program which assist in learning process and helps in effective delivery of instruction. The study described the LMS relative to aim, delivery and interactivity as well as determined the extent of application of LMS relative to curriculum, pedagogy and evaluation. The responses of the administrators and faculty members were compared. Likewise, it also determined the problems and challenges were further identified. The descriptive method of research was utilized in this study. A research – made questionnaire was the main data –gathering instrument complemented by interviews and focus group discussion. Respondents were 182 faculty members and 29 administrators including the Deans, Associate Deans, Department chairpersons, and ICT Head/Coordinators in HEIs. Weighted mean, frequency, percentage and t –test was utilized as statistical tools to treat gathered data. The findings revealed that Learning Management System is an interactive platform that is design to effectively manage lesson content for easy access and use by teachers and learners using any digital device through the Web. Learning Management System is applied in HEIs using a variety of media platforms in preparing interactive and engaging lessons presentation and maintain students record. Insufficient time to plan technology lessons and resistance to change among teachers are the common problems in the LMS application while accessibility to ICT materials and sustainability of training on pedagogic and digital literacy is the top most challenges. Lastly, the proposed management plan includes important various activities and strategies focusing on key areas in instruction such as curriculum, pedagogy and evaluation for sustainable utilization of LMS in HEIs.

Keywords: Learning Management System, Higher Education Institutions, descriptive method, Philippines